

Title: Advertising in the Age of AI

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INTRODUCTION:

AI is significant redefining what brands can or cannot do with the customer experience. AI allows companies to use data already at their disposal to measure in real time, learn more about the customer and anticipate what happens next. Nearly six in 10 CMOs believe that within the next five years, companies will need to compete in the AI space to succeed. We still have challenges ahead as consumers may seem ready for AI, but they have concerns trusting the technology. Therefore, there could not be a better time to define AI and explain its potential in advertising more clearly.

AIM:

- Learn about the major challenges faced by today's digital marketers
- What AI and Machine Learning are
- The current uses of AI in advertising
- How AI will continue to influence advertising this year and beyond

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Survey, markets trends, expert interviews and case studies

In 2017, Sysomos surveyed over 200 marketing professionals to gain a deeper understanding of how marketers view AI, how actively they are investigating the use of AI and whether the rise of AI will lead to job losses.

RESULTS:

85% believe that AI is going to make a significant impact on their marketing activity over the next five years. Over half (61%) of marketers believe the integration of AI will result a loss of jobs. But when it comes to creativity, 63% are confident that it will not become automated by AI.

CONCLUSIONS:

Marketers are excited by the possibilities of incorporating AI into their marketing strategies. Over half of our respondents believe the use of AI will lead to greater efficiencies, productivity and generate new ideas and opportunities. But there are obstacles to overcome. Just over half of marketing professionals understand the capabilities of AI and just over a third are actively

investigating its potential use cases – which shows further education needs to be done in order to maximise AIs full capabilities

KEYWORDS:

AI, Advertising, Customer Experience

BIOGRAPHY:

Alberto is an Executive Director of Strategy & Planning at Ogilvy. In this role, he provides strategic advice for consumer experience planning and relationship management. Alberto has 15 years of experience leading strategic engagements in branding, customer research and digital experience in global markets spanning the US and Latin America. Prior to joining Ogilvy, he ran communications planning for clients such as HP Enterprise, American Express, and the US Army. He holds an MPA in International Economic Policy from Columbia University, MS in Integrated Marketing Communications from Northwestern University, an MBA in Operations Management from Loyola University Chicago.